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The Problem of Associating Elaziğ Korucutepe Elite Burial Chambers with Kurgan Tombs

Korucutepe Elit Mezarlarının Kurgan Mezarlarla İlişkilendirilme Sorunsalı

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Öz: Towards the end of the IVth millennium B.C., the communities living in the Eastern Anatolia Region went through a transformation towards an urban culture as a result of the cultural change and transformation experienced in the region. It is observed that with urbanization, privileged families and groups were formed within the cities. We see the first burial tradition of an elite class that incorporates a belief in the hereafter among the peoples of Eastern Anatolia in the elite tombs of Korucutepe, which date back to the second half of the IVth millennium B.C. In these two-chamber tombs made of adobe, numerous unique artifacts were recovered along with the deceased. Rich burial gifts reveal that a radical social and economic change took place in the region. Considering both chronological, rich grave goods and burial structures, these tombs, associated with Mesopotamia-Syria, Transcaucasia, and northeastern Iranian cultures, are understood to have unique local characteristics. However, in recent studies, these tombs have been associated especially with kurgan tombs.

Anahtar sözcükler: Korucutepe, Chamber Tomb, Kurgan Tomb, Elite, Eastern Anatolia-Transcaucasia

Abstract: MÖ IV. binyılın sonlarına doğru Doğu Anadolu Bölgesi'nde kültürel değişim ve dönüşümün yaşanması ile birlikte bölgede yaşayan topluluklar, şehir kültürüne yönelik bir dönüşüm gerçekleştirmiştir. Şehirleşmeyle birlikte kentler içinde ayrıcalıklı ailelerin, zümrelerin oluştuğu anlaşılmaktadır. Doğu Anadolu halkları arasında bu elit sınıfın öteki dünya inancıyla bütünleşen ilk ölü gömme geleneğine, MÖ IV. binyıl ikinci yarısına tarihlenen Korucutepe'deki elit mezarlarda tanık oluyoruz. Kerpiçten örülüşlü iki odalı bu mezarlarda, ölen kişilerle birlikte çok sayıda eşsiz eser ele geçmiştir. Zengin ölü hediyeleri bu bölgede radikal sosyal, ekonomik bir dönüşümün yaşandığını bize göstermektedir. Mezopotamya-Suriye, Transkafkasya ve Kuzeydoğu İran kültürleriyle ilişkilendirilen bu mezarların, hem kronolojik hem zengin mezar eşyaları, hem de mezar yapısı bir arada ele alındığında özgün yerel özellikler taşıdığı anlaşılmaktadır. Ancak son yıllarda yapılan bilimsel çalışmalarda bu mezarlar, özellikle de kurgan mezarlarla ilişkilendirme yoluna gidilmektedir.

Keywords: Korucutepe, Oda Mezar, Kurgan Mezar, Elit, Doğu Anadolu-Transkafkasya

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Introduction

Chamber tombs began to be used for “*Ancestor Cult*” and “*Family Tombs*” where multiple burials were undertaken. While some of them were made of mud-brick and stone above ground, others were built of stone and wood underground. When the material and labor force exerted in these tombs are taken into consideration, it is seen that much greater effort is needed than other tombs. It is also likely to see several valuable artifacts in these tombs, which were built for elite people as a tribute to their deeds. It is clear that these types of tombs, which contain monumental characteristics, were adopted for people or families from the upper class. The fact that they are spotted in different places and less in number compared to the tombs classified in the same period confirms the existence of a privileged social group of elites¹.

These tombs are often confused with kurgan-type tombs. Kurgan tombs also contain chambers, but their chambers are built under piles of stones and soil. This tomb type, which had not been used by the peoples of the Eastern Anatolia until the IInd millennium BC, must have been brought by the folks who entered Anatolia through Transcaucasia². However, it should be especially noted that this type of tomb was not used by the peoples of the Elazığ-Malatya Section even at the beginning of the IInd millennium BC. In this case, it is quite compelling to search for the root of kurgan tomb culture in Korucutepe and Arslantepe tombs, which were not used even in the IIIrd and IInd millennium BC.

It is no wonder that there were significant changes and transformations in the settlements of the Eastern Anatolia dating to the end of the IVth millennium B.C. While the region maintained its strong communication network with the Mesopotamian communities, their cultural interactions with Transcaucasia also continued to increase. In the settlements dating to this period in the Elazığ-Malatya Section, strong data have been reached revealing a rise in the production and use of metal works. Unearthed offerings to the dead in the elite tombs of the main centers such as Korucutepe and its successor Arslantepe indicate the leap in the development of metal production. Apart from the metal artifacts found in these tombs, other metal artifacts and crucibles uncovered in other settlements from the same period are noteworthy. It should also be highlighted that this region is rich in mineral resources. All these data turn the direction of mineral processing workshops, which are sought elsewhere outside the region, again to this area³. Moreover, the metal artifacts found in the kurgan tombs in Transcaucasia are scarce in general. When all these data are taken into account, it is quite problematic to associate the Korucutepe elite tomb with the kurgan tombs of Transcaucasia.

Materials and Method

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to unfold the significance of the Korucutepe elite tomb, which played a key role in illuminating the Late Chalcolithic Age of the Upper Euphrates Basin. Its architectural characteristics and burial details were analyzed in-depth along with the unearthed artifacts from it. No similar tomb was found in its immediate vicinity before and in the same chronology. So, the only tomb within the closest date range was the Arslantepe elite tomb. Firstly, these two tombs were compared in terms of their location, type, finds, and burial cultures in the settlements. Possible similarities and differences were discussed. Later, after investigations in the surrounding areas, kurgan graves in Transcaucasia and the very similar family graves in northwest Iran were reached. Especially in recent years, the Korucutepe elite tomb, which has been compared

¹ Parliti & Uhri 2018, 4-6, fig. 2; Aydın-Tavukçu & Avli 2021, 68.

² Sagona & Zimansky 2009, 190.

³ Kökten 1947, 461.

with kurgan tombs by researchers, has been reevaluated based on chronology, architectural features, tomb finds, and persons. With this method, it was explored whether the elite tomb in Korucutepe overlapped with the kurgan tombs in Transcaucasia. Besides, one-to-one correlations were made with the elite tombs in northwest Iran. When strong ties could not be established between the elite tombs of both regions, the centers in the south of the Euphrates Basin were investigated within the scope of the literature. The tombs here were evaluated with the Korucutepe elite tombs regarding their location, architectural features, tomb finds, characteristics of the burials.

Korucutepe Elite Tombs

Korucutepe Mound is located within the Eski Aşağı İçme village, 30 km' east of Elaziğ province. Burney was the first archeologist to visit this mound, which is located in the fertile Altinova, suitable for settlement. Excavations were started by Van Loon the following year (1968). Ertem undertook the excavations that Van Loon continued until 1973 between 1973 and 1975⁴.

Fig. 1. a-b. Family grave no. 1 (Van Loon & Guterbock 1972, Lev. 54,2; Van Loon 1978, Plt. 79b); c-d. Family grave no. 2 (Van Loon 1978, Plate. 79c; Van Loon & Buccelatti 1969, Fig. 1)

It is mentioned that in the northwest part of Korucutepe Mound, there is a part reserved for a graveyard between the settlements dated to the end of the IVth millennium B.C. and the beginning of the IIIrd millennium B.C.⁵. During the 1970 excavations, two extraordinary mud-brick chamber tombs were encountered on the upper level of a house that was repeatedly repaired within the Late Chalcolithic period niche, which reached two meters in thickness in this part of the mound. Pottery graves belonging to an adult woman, a man, and a child were uncovered in the first of these two adobe-built elite chamber tombs, which have not been clarified yet but are stated to be inside the

⁴ Burney 1958, map. 3, fig. 182; Van Loon & Buccelatti 1969, 79; Ertem 1982, 2.

⁵ Ertem 1982, 2.

settlement⁶. The three people in the first tomb with a rectangular plan and the gifts to accompany them constitute the first example of the region's burial traditions. One of the burials here belongs to a man. It is significant that a wand/ball head made of raw iron was found next to this man's head in the form of a mace. Moreover, a silver bracelet and a copper dagger were left in the grave as a dead gift. Miniature metal artifacts were also found next to this dagger with a silver spine, weighing 400 gr. at the chest level of the man⁷ (Fig. 1a-b; Fig. 2).

A unique silver bracelet was unearthed around the shoulder of the 18-21-year-old woman, whose head was destroyed by a pit dug in the late period, next to the male burial. This bracelet has a print seal facet for use. This is a sign of a social structure in which the woman might be a ruler. There is an engraved figurine in the shape of a wild goat on the seal⁸. Besides this special find, terracotta pots were arranged around the wall in the burial chamber. Disc-shaped bone beads, silver rings, and moon-shaped necklace among the ornaments show how wealthy this woman was when she was alive⁹ (Fig. 2). Considering the upper part of the elite woman damaged by the late period pit, it is likely that many more precious gifts were destroyed. Because we know that the dead offerings were left especially around the head and neck of women. Heaps of copper were left next to the pottery where the child was placed in this elite family tomb¹⁰.

Adjacent to the first family tomb, there is the second adobe chamber tomb, which was carefully built. This tomb, which is associated with the first chamber tomb, belongs only to a woman. She must have been the ancestor of the other people in the adjacent family cemetery. Along with her, hundreds of small beads made of limestone, carnallite, and bone were found. These beads belonged to the pieces of the belt, bracelet, and anklet that adorned her while she was being placed in the grave. Many metal works were found in this tomb. Among these are a silver diadem, a silver moon-shaped throat guard, and hair rings. As in the family tomb in the first burial chamber, these unique artifacts found together with a lone woman, point to the first noble individuals of the region¹¹ (Fig. 1c-d; Fig. 2). The differences in the numbers, ages, genders, and grave gifts of the people in these cemeteries can be related to their social status and political power.

Fig. 2. Grave offerings of the Korucutepe elite tomb (Van Loon & Guterbock 1972, Fig. 55,1; Van Loon 1978, Plt. 109, 110/1, 111 a)

The Problem of Associating the Korucutepe Elite Tomb with Kurgan Tombs

Considering the location of the Korucutepe elite tomb, the way it was built, and the rather valuable

⁶ Van Loon & Guterbock 1972a, 80.

⁷ Van Loon & Guterbock 1972a, 80.

⁸ Van Loon & Guterbock 1972a, 80, pl. 54.2/55.1; Van Loon & Guterbock 1972b, 127-128, fig. 2-3.

⁹ Van Loon & Guterbock, 1972a, 80.

¹⁰ Yakar 1984, 67.

¹¹ Van Loon & Guterbock 1972a, 79-80, pl. 54.2; Van Loon 1973, 360; Van Loon 1973, 360; Van Loon 1978, 10, 61, pl. 7; Van Loon & Guterbock 1972b, 128.

and unique grave offerings presented to the rulers in the tomb, we can suggest that they were built in the period from the middle of the IVth millennium B.C. to the beginning of the IIIrd millennium B.C. Although the tomb was dated to 3000 B.C. by its digger, some scientists dated Korucutepe to both Phase B and Phase C (3500-3200 B.C.)¹². In a study, the two-room family tombs containing women, men, and children who were buried with numerous special artifacts and silver ornaments were dated to Phase B of Korucutepe. Shanshashvili also claims that this phase should be dated between 3500-3000 B.C.¹³. In another study, this tomb was dated to the end of the IVth millennium B.C. and the beginning of the IIIrd millennium B.C., both as a type of tomb and the artifacts found in it especially iron staff and silver artifacts¹⁴. These dates are very essential for our study. Since there are not such rich family graves in Transcaucasia between these date ranges, it is difficult to locate any tombs that can be associated with Korucutepe. Apart from the fact that there are no examples in such a far-reaching area, no similar particularly valuable artifacts were found in the Korucutepe elite tomb. All these data reveal that the communities of both regions were not in close contact, as some researchers claimed. In our opinion, both cultures communicated through intermediaries and these intermediaries also played a key role in the exchange of material works.

The reason why the Korucutepe elite tomb was compared to the kurgan tombs, especially in terms of the way they were built is controversial. Some researchers, unfortunately, act ideologically and search almost all of the unique culture of Anatolia in Transcaucasia. However, they cannot build their archaeological evidence on solid foundations. And, they try to establish similarities in terms of the construction technique of two adjacent chamber tombs found in Korucutepe. Based on the wooden entrance holes found just above the tomb chambers of the elites and the carbonized wooden remains uncovered in the tomb, it is understood that the tombs were terminated with a roof¹⁵. Due to this construction technique, some researchers have compared elite tombs with kurgans. They claim that these tomb finds reflect the later typical Transcaucasian burial tradition similar to those of Transcaucasia when they were first unearthed. The kurgan tombs of Transcaucasia are also made in the form of multiple burials, together with individuals with grave gifts. These tombs were opened underground like wells and then closed with stones and soil¹⁶. For instance, the underground burial chamber of the Menteş Tepe Kurgan was rectangular and the room was entered with a dromos¹⁷. Şadli/Shadly kurgans have a rectangular chamber inside the burial pit with a depth of 1.5 meters. The chamber tomb was later covered with soil and pebbles¹⁸. The Kakheti kurgans consist of a round chamber tomb inside a three-meter pit¹⁹. After the main soil of Tallinn's kurgan tomb was opened, a burial chamber was made of large stones. The chamber tomb was entered through the dromos²⁰. However, the chamber tombs in Korucutepe present a very different architectural technique. Although the Korucutepe elite tomb rises on flat ground, it does not have an entrance like a dromos. No masonry stone was used in its construction. No wood was used in interior architecture either. Only wood was utilized to carry the roof. This is quite natural because archaeological excavations illustrate that the peoples living between the date range of the Korucutepe elite tombs used tree trunks as the load-bearing beams for the roofs of their houses²¹.

¹² In Phase C, EBA I-IIA levels were dated to 3,160-2,900 and 2,680-2,610 BC, see. Van Loon & Guterbock 1972a, 80.

¹³ Shanshashvili 2010, 170.

¹⁴ Parliti & Yücel 2020, 225-226; Parliti 2020, 342.

¹⁵ Van Loon & Guterbock 1972a, 80, p. 54.2/55,1; Van Loon & Guterbock 1972b, 127-128, fig. 2-3.

¹⁶ Sagona 2010, 44.

¹⁷ Poulmarc'h 2014, 139-140, fig. 61-63.

¹⁸ Jalilov 2015, 156-160, fig. 1-2/7-8.

¹⁹ Dedabrashvili 1979, 19-22, tab. IV/LXIV.

²⁰ Avetis *et al.* 2010, 161-164, fig. 1-3.

²¹ It has been determined that the upper roofs of the collapsed houses of Korucutepe, which are dated to the IIIrd

In this case, it is quite reasonable for them to use this technique, which they use in daily life, in the construction of the burial chamber.

Despite all these data, it is stated that the elite tombs of Korucutepe are family burials and that the architectural characteristics of the tomb and the unique gifts for the dead reflect the burial traditions of Transcaucasia²². Comparing this tomb with the kurgans in the Caucasus, Palumbi also describes it as an “elite tomb” built of mud brick, which matches the tomb given to the 9-11 levels of Tepe Gawra (Mesopotamia)²³. It is stated that the valuable burial discoveries found in the mudbrick tomb of Korucutepe are similar to those of Tureng Tepe, except Tepe Gawra²⁴. Besides, these tombs reflect the new burial traditions and an extension of the tradition of the (Transcaucasian) kurgan with a wooden roof, which was built underground with the Syro-Mesopotamian influence. The elite tombs of Korucutepe, which are associated with the kurgan tombs and the elite tombs in Mesopotamia, show that at the end of the IVth millennium B.C., they turned into a central hub that had contact with both the south and the east of their vicinity²⁵. They are also associated with the north of Iran with a brightly colored vessel found in elite tombs possessing a wooden roofed burial chamber and kurgan characteristics²⁶.

The elite tombs of Korucutepe are also compared with the stone cist tomb of Arslantepe, which is also associated with the kurgan tombs. Unlike other tombs in the area, the elite tombs in Korucutepe and Arslantepe have extraordinary burial gifts and are located in unique and special places within the settlement²⁷. Yakar implied that the tradition of such burials in Anatolia began with the kurgan migrations²⁸. However, there is no real evidence that the elite tombs of both Arslantepe and Korucutepe were inspired by migration from other regions in their architectural formation. Moreover, the owners of these tombs were in the position of representatives of the wealthiest people in their domain. It is quite normal for these elites to need such a monumental tomb. Trying to associate the elite tombs in Eastern Anatolia with the Transcaucasian or Maykop tombs in terms of type²⁹ is a challenging approach.

When it is difficult to relate the elite tombs in Eastern Anatolia with regard to architecture, they are compared with the artifacts reserved to accompany the dead³⁰. However, it is claimed that the elite tombs themselves and the gifts in the tombs are local productions based on the crucibles, furnaces, and slags found in the settlements in the Elaziğ-Malatya Section³¹. In addition, it should be underlined that such rich and numerous pieces dating as early as Korucutepe could not be found neither in the settlements nor the tombs in the Transcaucasia. The elite tombs of Korucutepe and Arslantepe will be discussed in detail below.

millennium BC, were supported by tree trunks such as ash, elm and poplar, see. Van Loon & Guterbock 1972a, 80; The roofs of the houses of Şemsiyetepe belonging to the IVth and IIIrd millennium BC were also supported with wooden beams and beam poles. Darga 1986, 120; 1987, 159; Parliti & Caner 2021, 37.

²² Parliti 2020, 628-629.

²³ Palumbi 2011, 213.

²⁴ Shanshashvili 2010, 170.

²⁵ Palumbi 2011, 213.

²⁶ Yakar 1985, 269-270.

²⁷ Parliti & Yücel 2021, 103-104.

²⁸ Yakar 1981, 103.

²⁹ Sagona & Zimansky 2009, 190; Palumbi 2008, 150-151.

³⁰ Marro 2011, 298, fig. 12.3.

³¹ Çiğdem 2014, 49, 81.

Distinctiveness of the Korucutepe Elite Tomb in Eastern Anatolian Archeology

It is stated that in the IVth millennium B.C. there was a strong detachment among the communities in Eastern Anatolia. In this process, it is seen that the local communities in the Elaziğ-Malatya Section had strong connections with Syria and Mesopotamia for both political and cultural development. With the rich tombs and monumental architecture unearthed in Korucutepe, they are the earliest noble tombs that exhibit a great transformation and the emergence of local elites³². Hundreds of limestone beads, carnallite and bone bead artifacts belonging to belts, foot, and arm bracelets found in the chamber tomb belonging to the woman are remarkable. Silver diadem, moon-shaped necklace, and hair rings are among the special finds. The raw mace head, silver bracelet, and copper dagger belonging to the man in the elite tomb are indicative of power. The terracotta pots lined up around this elite tomb should be seen as the common property of the family. Special items unearthed inside the elite tomb unite different regions in one center. In this sense, it is possible to say that people who specialize in mining were trained in this place and that these people served especially the elites. These elite families had the power to access metal artifacts, precious stones, and exotic goods. They could also communicate with distant lands in line with their needs or desires for these goods. Korucutepe, the earliest tomb example in Eastern Anatolia, proves that certain people among the settlers became rich with the dynamics of the economic system created³³. In this case, it is possible to attribute the presence of precious metals, stones and exotic goods found on the people in the mudbrick elite tombs of Korucutepe-brought from distant lands depending on the demands of the elite groups- to the birth of the elites in the Elaziğ-Malatya Section.

The elite tomb discovered in the center of Arslantepe right after Korucutepe confirms that privileged groups were formed among the people who gained power in this region³⁴. It is understood that the terracotta pots, metal vessels, bronze-silver pins, gold-silver necklaces, metal necklaces, bracelets, spirals and silver hair rings, silver-copper crowns/pediments, silver-copper crowns, silver-plated necklaces, copper belts, silver rings, silver-copper daggers and spears buried to accompany the dead in the tombs of Korucutepe and Arslantepe are the jewelry items used by the elites in their daily life. Metal artifacts found in the stone cist tomb of Arslantepe and the mudbrick chamber tomb of Korucutepe -bronze, silver needles, gold silver necklaces, metal necklaces, silver ring (Arslantepe) and silver bracelet (Korucutepe), silver crown/diadems, belts and metal resources such as carnallite and rock crystal- are interpreted as signs of common tastes and productions. It is also stated that it is not a coincidence that so many common productions were found together in both tombs. The biggest difference between the tombs in terms of the number of works is the quantity of the artifacts available in Arslantepe. Furthermore, almost all of the items left to accompany the dead, except the silver seal and iron mace in the elite tomb of Korucutepe, were found in Arslantepe elite tomb. While the qualities of their finds are similar, it is seen that the quantities are different³⁵.

It is stated that silver jewelry, iron mace, and other ornaments dating to the IVth millennium B.C. are unlikely to be of local production. Although it is suggested that new settlers may have come to the region from Transcaucasia, based on this view, such treasures are not uncounted in the contemporary tombs of Transcaucasia. In addition, when this situation is considered on the basis of settlements, the amount of metal finds in settlements and tombs in Transcaucasia compared to Eastern Anatolia is pretty limited³⁶. In this case, we can say more clearly that the owners of

³² Palumbi 2008, 54.

³³ Palumbi 2011, 213.

³⁴ Arsebük 1986, 67-69.

³⁵ Parliti *et al.* 2021, 631-632.

³⁶ Sagona & Sagona 2009, 541-542.

Korucutepe and Arslantepe elite tombs, which were found in the west of the Kura-Araxes cultural geography, became prosperous by establishing commercial relations with their neighbors in both internal and external dominions. Çiğdem approaches this situation a little differently and states that a silver bracelet belonging to a man, a silver bracelet of a woman, and various objects made of silver in Korucutepe chamber tombs are the first silver finds of Anatolia (IVth millennium B.C.)³⁷. This situation also indicates that elites might have become rich by using, processing, and distributing local resources.

Considering the archaeological findings unearthed in settlements such as Arslantepe, Norşuntepe, and Tepecik with the example of Korucutepe, we can contend that an elite group was formed based on the developed interregional trade network and advanced mining technology. The presence of such chamber tombs made of adobe or stone in Anatolia and Mesopotamia since the IVth millennium B.C. denotes that the elite family tradition started in a vast expanse of land, not in a core region. Since the grave offerings uncovered in all of these tombs are an indicator of wealth, it can be said that these tombs belong to elite people. One of the earliest examples of adobe or stone chamber tombs belonging to the elite was found on floors 8-11 of Tepe Gawra. The tomb in question, which is dated to the middle of the IVth millennium B.C., reveals both the special architecture in its construction and the gifts accompanying the dead in the tomb. Numerous artifacts made of turquoise, ebony, obsidian, carnallite, lapis lazuli, silver, and gold were found in each of these tombs. These are probably attachments to the clothes or parts of the diadems³⁸. It is considered that the elites buried in this tomb were high-ranking people in their community. The closest one similar to this type of tombs of Tepe Gawra is the mudbrick chamber tombs unearthed in Korucutepe. The fact that these tombs were built of mud brick with multiple burials exhibits parallelism with the rich burial gifts inside³⁹.

Results

A noteworthy group of family tombs was unearthed at Korucutepe in Elazığ, Malatya's neighbor. The family, the burial tradition and the burial gifts found in it partially reflect the Transcaucasian burial tradition. However, they are considered as an extension of the kurgan tradition, as they are built underground with a wooden roof⁴⁰. This tomb was also compared with the Mesopotamian finds of Tepe Gawra and Tureng Tepe. This center with a combination of a tomb architecture resembling a kurgan and Mesopotamian tomb type, reflects the south and east communication network of the region through the end of the IVth millennium B.C.⁴¹. The architectural characteristics of the Korucutepe elite tomb are associated with the Transcaucasian influence, and the gifts are mostly associated with the Mesopotamian-Syrian influence. An example of a brightly colored vessel found in the tombs is associated with the north of Iran⁴². But, the chamber tombs of the elites in Korucutepe must have been built with internal dynamics, since they are the first in terms of both chronology and richness of the finds. Apart from this, it is seen that the elite ruling family tradition continued, especially after the overlapping finds in the Arslantepe royal tomb. The elite tombs of Korucutepe and Arslantepe reflect the existence of privileged people who gained power in the Elazığ-Malatya Section⁴³.

³⁷ Çiğdem 2014, 45.

³⁸ Palumbi 2011, 213.

³⁹ Van Loon 1978, 61, pl. 79 B, C; Palumbi 2011, 213.

⁴⁰ Parliti & Yücel 2021, 111, 118.

⁴¹ Palumbi 2011, 213.

⁴² Yakar 1985, 269-270.

⁴³ Arsebük 1986, 67-69.

However, it should be noted that even if the elite tombs in Korucutepe and Arslantepe are compared to each other, the stone cist graves of Arslantepe were built in a pit⁴⁴, while the chamber tombs of Korucutepe were built with mudbrick blocks on flat ground. When we take a look at the tombs resembling a room in Transcaucasia, we see that they are shaped with stone rows and display very different architectural characteristics. Both the form features and the materials used in the construction of these tombs are quite different from the chamber tombs in Anatolia⁴⁵. Two elite tombs built of adobe, which can be associated with the two elite tombs of Korucutepe in terms of form, construction material, and partially valuable metal artifacts, were discovered on Köhneh Pasgah Tepesi in Northwest Iran. In the southern part of Pasgah, two rectangular-planned mud-brick chamber tombs were encountered. It was determined that wood was used to hold the roofs of these two tombs. Arm ring, two earrings, three beads, three terracotta pots, bronze spearheads, axes, and arrowheads used as a weapon show that they belong to elite people⁴⁶.

The defensive walls of centers such as Korucutepe and Arslantepe and the discovery of the elite tombs inside large-scale settlements provide the existence of settled cities. Based on the Arslantepe stone cist tomb and the valuable gifts in it, the history of the systematic and great colonial movements, which is thought to have started in the IIIrd millennium B.C., should be dated to the middle of the IVth millennium B.C. due to the Korucutepe elite tombs and the valuable gifts inside. This innovative development in the IVth millennium B.C. must have made some centers more advanced than others. Because we can foresee that some families who managed to be the organizers of networks in these centers became wealthy and had a say in the society and turned into the elitist class that held the administration in their hands. The fact that very few tombs have pieces of evidence showing the political dominance of the rulers in which they were strengthened by combining military and religious powers, reveals the importance of the tomb we have discussed. Crowns, scepters, waist belts, special vessels, and metal weapons found with the persons in the elite tombs support this situation. Based on time and effort spent in the construction as well as the building materials of the tombs, we can claim that the social class distinction became evident over time. As a result, the elite tombs of Korucutepe, which can be dated till the middle of the IVth millennium B.C., are the first and strongest representatives of division, innovation and transformation that began to be experienced in Eastern Anatolia.

⁴⁴ Frangipane 2001, 2-7.

⁴⁵ For detailed information, see Poulmarc'h 2014, tab. 7-9.

⁴⁶ Işıklı *et al.* 2019, 322.

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